

DETERMINATION AND VARIABILITY OF QUANTITATIVE INDICATORS OF WINTER WHEAT

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract..

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INTRODUCTION

When evaluating breeding materials, plant varieties, and choosing them, attention should be paid to quantitative indicators (yield, productivity elements).

Quantitative indicators include the hereditary capabilities of the plant under the influence of the environment. In this state, their variability is natural. The traits that can be influenced by the environment are little changeable, which depends on the genotype. Conducting a selection with highly changing indicators may not always give a positive result. For this reason, quantitative indicators of a plant are one of the complex objects of quantitative genetics and breeding. In turn, as noted above, the strong variability of quantitative indicators creates certain difficulties when working with them. The emergence of modern information technologies in our life served as a positive solution to this problem. It became possible to widely use statistical methods in biological research. As a result, changes were noted in the structure and degree of correlations between quantitative indicators under the influence of external factors. Also, an increase in the degree of correlations between quantitative indicators in adverse conditions was determined. Along with this, it was revealed that the variability of quantitative indicators occurs, agreed as well as. Also, an increase in the degree of correlations between quantitative indicators in adverse conditions was determined. Along with this, it was revealed that the variability of quantitative indicators occurs, is consistent and also independent with other signs. . [1, c. 308; 2, c. 20-21; 3, c. 45-47; 4, c. 84-90].

The main purpose of this study is to study the effect of the fungicide on the degree of correlation between the quantitative indicators of winter wheat. This kind of research is carried out for the first time in the conditions of the Syrdarya region.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Winter wheat varieties such as Tanya, Dustlik, Krasnodar and Chillaki were chosen as experimental objects. 6 quantitative indicators of these varieties were studied. Observations were carried out on an experimental plot of medium salinity at Gulistan State University. All phenological observations and calculations were carried out [6, p. 147] based on the guidelines of UzNIIKh. When calculating the coefficients of correlation (r), determination (r²) and variability between the studied characteristics, a statistical program was used SPSS-14[5, c. 107]. The determination of indicators was determined by the formulas R² ch, R² m, and the distance between them $d=1-r$ [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained showed that fungicides affect the formation of quantitative indicators of winter wheat. This can be seen from the following table. If the height of the plant in the control is on average 91.97 cm, then under the influence of CDH (cobalt diglycyrhizinate) it is 87.81 cm. This shows a decrease in plant height of 4 cm compared to the control. If the number of productive ears in the control is 1.58, then under the influence of KDH it will be 1.71. It follows that the number of productive ears of winter wheat under the influence of cobalt diglycyrhizinate increases. Exactly the same results were noted for the weight of the ear, the number of grains and the weight of 1000 grains. The degree of rust infection under control was 38.80%, and under the influence of KDH 19.97%. Under the influence of CDG, the degree of yellow rust infection of winter wheat varieties decreased by 20.0%. Statistical analysis of the original data determined the effect of the fungicide on the variability of winter wheat quantitative indicators.

The variability and determinism of quantitative indicators of winter wheat are shown in Figures 1-2. According to the figure, the quantitative indicators of winter wheat showed strong variability and determination of rust infection (6) (numbers indicate signs) (1-figure).

Table -1

Quantitative indicators of winter wheat under the influence of cobalt diglycyrhizinate

No	Statistical indicators	Plant height, cm	Heading (pieces)	Weight of the 1st ear, g	The number of grains in one ear, pieces	Weight of 1000 grains, G	Rust infection, %
In control (by variety)							
1	Average	91,97±1,42	1,58±0,05	1,29±0,03	19,17± 0,48	41,20± 0,19	38,80± 1,64
2	Minimum	77,50	1,00	1,00	15,00	38,00	28,00
3	Maximum	105,20	2,60	1,90	26,00	43,50	57,00
Under the influence of KDH							

1	Average	87,81±1,45	1,71±0,08	2,11±0,05	29,55±0,63	44,92±0,40	19,97±1,50
2	Minimu	74,60	1,00	1,20	21,00	41,30	8,00
3	Maximum	101,20	2,80	2,90	35,00	49,20	38,00

This shows that rust infection of winter wheat varieties is largely dependent on the environment. It was found that plant height (1), tillering (2), ear weight (3) and the number of grains per ear (4) are subject to strong determination. In this case, the variability of these quantitative indicators is associated with the genotype. Of the studied quantitative traits, the weight of 1000 grains was found to be little deterministic and little changeable. This indicates that this quantitative trait has the property of independent variability. Under the influence of cobalt diglycyrrhizinate, corresponding changes in the variability of the quantitative traits of wheat were noted (2-figure). The degree of rust infestation (6) was found to be highly variable and deterministic. This means that infection with rust of signs of winter wheat depends more on the genotype. Here, too, plant height (1), harvest (2), ear weight (3) and number of grains per ear (4) are subject to strong determination. The weight of 1000 grains was found to be the least deterministic and little changeable.

Figure 1. Variability (CV, %) and determination (r2) of winter wheat quantitative traits (control)

The numbers indicate the signs. 1-plant height, 2-tillering, 3-weight of one ear, 4-number of grains in one ear, 5-weight of 1000 grains, 6-rust infection.

Cobalt diglycyrrhizinate affects not only the variability of quantitative traits of winter wheat, but also the degree of correlation between them (3-figure).

Figure 2. Variability (CV, %) and determinism (r^2) of winter wheat quantitative traits (under the influence of CDG)

The numbers indicate the signs. 1-plant height, 2-tillering, 3-weight of one ear, 4-number of grains in one ear, 5-weight of 1000 grains, 6-rust infection.

In the control, a strong correlation was noted between the height (1) and tillering (2) of the plant. This means that the number of collections of tall plants was large. Exactly the same result was obtained between the weight of grain in one ear (3) and the amount of grain in one ear (4). In tall plants, the weight of 1000 grains was heavier. This is due to the correlation of the average degree between these features. Plants with heavy spikes and more grains had less rust infestation. The reason for this is the negative relationship between these traits, i.e. between 3 and 6 and 4 and 6.

Analyzing the degree of correlation between the quantitative characteristics of winter wheat under the influence of cobalt diglycyrhizinate, according to the figure, we saw the changes that occurred compared to the control (3-figure). In this variant, a strong (correlation coefficient was more than 0.7) correlation between the height (1) and the collection (2) of the plant was noted. It follows that the degree of strong correlation between plant height and tillering was preserved in both cases.

If under supervision between collection (2) and ear weight (3) a weak correlation was noted, then under the influence of cobalt diglycyrhizinate a negative relationship was revealed. In the first variant, the increase in the number of collections caused an increase in the weight of the ear, and in the second, the opposite was observed.

Under supervision, there was a direct correlation between collection (2), number of grains (4), weight of 1000 grains (5) and rust infestation (6), and under the influence of CDG, an opposite correlation was observed between these traits. This indicates that under the influence of the fungicide, the number of productive stems of winter wheat varieties increased. As a result, the number of grains per ear (4) and the weight of 1000 grains (5) increased. It was also noted that plants less infected with rust had more productive stems. Between the weight of the ear (3), the number of grains per ear (4), similar quantitative characteristics and the degree of rust infection (6), a direct correlation was observed, and under supervision, an inverse correlation was observed.

Under the influence of the fungicide, a strong (correlation coefficient was greater than 0.7) correlation was determined between the weight of 1000 grains (5) and the degree of rust infection (6). Under supervision, the correlation coefficient between these indicators was found to be invalid. This means that under the

influence of cobalt diglycyrrhizinate, the degree of rust infection of winter wheat varieties decreases. This, in turn, serves to increase the mass of the grain.

If during the control the average coefficient of determination was equal to 0.28, then under the influence of the fungicide it was -0.17. It follows that rust creates unfavorable conditions for winter wheat varieties. This, in turn, served to increase the degree of correlations between quantitative characteristics. This can be explained from a scientific point of view by the proven increase in the degree of correlation between the quantitative traits of a plant under adverse conditions [1, p. 308]. Under the influence of cobalt diglycyrrhizinate, the number of rust infections of autumn wheat varieties decreased and favorable conditions for the plant appeared. As a result, there was a decrease in the degree of correlation between quantitative characteristics.

CONCLUSION

1. Cobalt diglycyrrhizinate affects the number of fertile stems of winter wheat varieties. Under the control, this indicator is 1.58, and under the influence of the fungicide it was 1.71.

2. It was determined that under control, the degree of rust infection is highly variable and little determined, and under the influence of the drug it is strongly determined. In the first case, rust infection of autumn wheat varieties depends more on the environment, and in the second case, on the genotype.

3. A strong correlation between the height of the plant and the amount of tillering was preserved in both cases.

4. The structure of correlations between the quantitative traits of winter wheat varieties is assigned to a group called "productivity".

5. Infection of winter wheat varieties with rust served to increase the degree of correlation between quantitative indicators. Under control, the average coefficient of determination was 0.28, and under the influence of cobalt diglycyrrhizinate it was 0.17. Under the influence of cobalt diglycyrrhizinate, wheat varieties were less infected with rust and favorable conditions for the plant appeared.

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